

A STUDY ON UNESCO'S ACTION PLAN FOR EDUCATION IN A POST-COVID WORLD

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Abstract :

The Corona virus pandemic has accentuated the reminder that pandemics have happened in the past and will continue to happen in the future. The current outbreak has severe social and economic consequences across the globe. It has short term and long term effects on trade education too. This research paper had tried to highlight the importance of UNESCO's action plan for education sector in a post COVID world in general to deal with repercussions of pandemic and ways to adjust in the new normal.

Key words: *Education, COVID 19, Pandemic, Measures, Action Plan*

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Introduction :

The COVID-19 pandemic has forced a massive shift away from learning and teaching in traditional settings with physical interactions. This is a major problem for children living in poverty worldwide, who often rely on the physical setting of their schools to provide educational materials, guidance, and, sometimes, the only decent meal of the day. In their homes, especially during times of confinement or quarantine, children can face multiple forms of abuse and violence.

Crowded conditions, a general lack of resources, particularly digital devices and connectivity, mean that typically the cost—in terms of education and general well-being—of the current health crisis will be highest for populations that are already vulnerable. For learners of all ages, as internships and apprenticeships have been cancelled, technical and vocational education programmes closed down, and community centres shuttered, it is those who have the least resources to begin with who will be harmed the most. These are problems that must be tackled now, lest disadvantage propel further disadvantages.

The current situations have created dangerous times for public education, with risks of fragmentation and unravelling as there is a chance to lose both teachers and students who may not return to schools once they reopen. A certain privatization occurs when learning moves from schools into the home. There is an immediate need to address the education of more than 1.5 billion students whose learning has been hampered due to school closures.

Amongst all this disparities, there is a need to recognize that many parents and communities have awakened to an appreciation of teachers' work and their professionalism. More and more people are becoming aware of the multiple roles that schools and colleges play in providing for the well-being of children and youth, and in ensuring health and nutrition, alongside academic learning. This increased awareness and appreciation can serve as the basis for a new revival of public education. This can be considered as a solidarity and a strong, resilient response to challenges in many societies. There is an increased attention to the public good and huge resourcefulness, dedication and creativity from the many teachers, families and students who are collaboratively building remarkable learning experiences. The research paper has focused on nine ideas for concrete actions of the International Commission on the Futures of Education—established by UNESCO in 2019 and composed of thought leaders from the worlds of academia, science, government, business. It focuses on education of today that will advance education tomorrow

Review of Literature :

1. **Bozkurt and Sharma (2020)** stressed on online environments that enable teachers to teach and interact with their students providing a variety of learning possibilities in a remote scenario. Issues of agency, responsibility, flexibility and choice are key elements which require 'careful planning, designing and determination that aims to create an effective learning ecology'.
2. **Fandino-Pérez (2020)** pointed out the significant role of virtuality of education and its position regarding personalized education, so demanded in times of normality, where teachers and students know each other, interact, and socialize, precisely the attitude that has taken away the virus. Perez also highlighted the distorted and absurd image of the work of teachers as producers of programming and good results, which turns them and their students into a kind of machine. Society has forgotten the main thing: to be human beings capable of creating a better world and of overcoming ignorance, fear, and demagoguery.
3. **Zhang et al. (2020)** focused on the difficulties associated with poor online teaching infrastructure, inexperience of teachers, the information gap (i.e., limited information and resources to all students) and the complex environment at home.

Objectives of the study :

1. To study the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on teaching learning and education system.
2. To suggest immediate action plan for concrete actions for rethinking education and reimagining how knowledge and learning can shape the future

Hypothesis of Study :

The COVID 19 Pandemic has adversely affected the Indian economy in general and different educational set ups in particular. The suggested measures can be a positive step for educational organisations towards reduction in ill effects in the era of new normal.

Research Methodology :

1. The present research paper is based on Primary and Secondary data.
2. Primary data is collected through observation method. Secondary data is collected through magazines, Research Papers, Newspaper articles and few websites.

Research Analysis :
UNESCO's Nine Ideas for Future Action for Education in post-COVID World :

1. **Commit to strengthen education as a common good.** Education is a bulwark against inequalities. In education as in health, we are safe when everybody is safe; we flourish when everybody flourishes.
2. **Expand the definition of the right to education** so that it addresses the importance of connectivity and access to knowledge and information. The Commission calls for a global public discussion—that includes, among others, learners of all ages—on ways the right to education needs to be expanded.
3. **Value the teaching profession and teacher collaboration.** There has been remarkable innovation in the responses of educators to the COVID-19 crisis, with those systems most engaged with families and communities showing the most resilience. We must encourage conditions that give frontline educators autonomy and flexibility to act collaboratively.
4. **Promote student, youth and children's participation and rights.** Intergenerational justice and democratic principles should compel us to prioritize the participation of students and young people broadly in the co-construction of desirable change.
5. **Protect the social spaces provided by schools as it transforms education.** The school as a physical space is indispensable. Traditional classroom organization must give way to a variety of ways of 'doing school' but the school as a separate space-time of collective living, specific and different from other spaces of learning must be preserved.
6. **Make free and open source technologies available to teachers and students.** Open educational resources and open access digital tools must be supported. Education cannot thrive with ready-made content built outside of the pedagogical space and outside of human relationships between teachers and students. Nor can education be dependent on digital platforms controlled by private companies.
7. **Ensure scientific literacy within the curriculum.** This is the right time for deep reflection on curriculum, particularly as we struggle against the denial of scientific knowledge and actively fight misinformation.
8. **Protect domestic and international financing of public education.** The pandemic has the power to undermine several decades of advances. National governments, international organizations, and all education and development partners must recognize the need to strengthen public health and social services but simultaneously mobilize around the protection of public education and its financing.

9. **Advance global solidarity to end current levels of inequality.** COVID-19 has shown us the extent to which our societies exploit power imbalances and our global system exploits inequalities. The Commission calls for renewed commitments to international cooperation and multilateralism, together with a revitalized global solidarity that has empathy and an appreciation of our common humanity at its core. COVID-19 presents us with a real challenge and a real responsibility. These ideas invite debate, engagement and action by governments, international organizations, civil society, educational professionals, as well as learners and stakeholders at all levels.

Limitations of the Study :

1. The study is based on observation method.
2. The Nine Ideas for Future Action considered in the study are general in nature and does not belong to a specific area of education.
3. It is more specifically for underdeveloped and developing economies

Findings of the Study :

1. The spiralling and unavoidable COVID-19 pandemic has distorted the planet's prospering education sector in tricky and uncertain terms.
2. The educational system has witnessed tremendous changes in the pandemic situations.

Suggestions of Study :

1. Decisions made today in the context of COVID-19 will have long-term consequences for the futures of education. Policy-makers, educators and communities must make highstakes choices today—these decisions should be guided by shared principles and visions of desirable collective futures.
2. In the renewal of education, human interaction and well-being must be given priority. Technology—particularly digital technology that enables communication, collaboration and learning across distance—is a formidable tool, not a panacea but a source of innovation and expanded potentials.
3. To safeguard the right to education under the extraordinary circumstances created by the pandemic, and to facilitate the levels of trust necessary for global collaboration in mobilizing resources to support the universal right to education, all education stakeholders should monitor the education resources which should be used for the sole purpose of advancing the interests and capabilities of learners. It is necessary to be especially vigilant of corruption and prevent the capture and diversion of education resources to advance private aims.

Conclusion :

The COVID-19 crisis has exposed the fact that innovation and creativity are broadly distributed and not the exclusive purview of select, well-resourced centres. IT is highly important to learn from and support the responses coming from teachers, students and communities—for in them lies the potential for transforming education during and after the present crisis.

These responses to the pandemic will be different from one place to another, from one context to another. But, they must be based on a humanistic vision of education and development and human rights frameworks. Actions must strengthen public education, fortify common goods and expand a global solidarity that emphasizes the collective responsibility for the education of everyone everywhere.

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Cite This Article:

Dr. Archana Kedar Prabhudesai, (2022). *A Study on UNESCO's Action Plan for Education in a post-COVID world, Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal, XI (II),35-39*